

OPTIMUM SELF-REFERENCE SPATIAL DIVERSITY PROCESSING FOR FDSS AND FH COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In 1996, a new spread spectrum communication system, called Frequency Diversity Spread Spectrum (FDSS), was proposed as a system to mitigate the problems of the common spread spectrum techniques. In this paper, two blind self-reference optimum beamforming methods tailored for the FDSS signalling scheme using the trivial repetition code are derived based on the inherent cross-correlation properties present among all the frequency bands. The method is also applicable to fast *Frequency Hopping* (FH) systems.

The proposed methods use the information of all the frequency bins jointly to yield optimum beamforming in the sense of maximum *Signal to Interference-plus-Noise Ratio* (SINR). One method computes all the beamvectors jointly performing a single generalized eigenvector computation. The other calculates each beamvector independently aiming at a parallel implementation. The two methods are analytically studied and tested via Monte-Carlo simulations. They are compared to other existing methods in terms of bit error rate, outperforming them and showing a performance close to the optimum value.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1996, a new spread spectrum communication system to counter bandlimited Gaussian interference, called Frequency Diversity Spread Spectrum (FDSS), was proposed [1]. It was devised as a system to mitigate the problems of the common spread spectrum techniques, namely, vulnerability of Direct Sequence to bandlimited partial-time (burst) jamming and of Frequency Hopping to partial-band interference [2, 3].

The FDSS signalling scheme basically consists on transmitting a coded version of the original signal over each band with an optional spreading stage (see Fig.1). However, only the trivial repetition code ($N, 1$) is considered herein. Therefore, the system can be seen as a simultaneous transmission of a signal over different non-overlapping frequency bands, providing the global signal structure with redundancy or diversity [4, 5, 6]. This redundancy can be related to the property of exact self-prediction, by which we can consider that the signal contains embedded self-references. The idea of using the inherent diversity of the signal structure to develop blind methods has also been applied in other areas such as equalization [7, 8], and beamforming in DS-CDMA [9, 10].

An optimum spatial processing approach for FDSS systems was proposed in [5], consisting on properly labeling a free and a hit band to apply then an algorithm based on the cross-correlation properties

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Figure 1: Scheme of the FDSS signal generation.

between these two diversity branches to compute the beamvectors for these two bands. Then, the output of the free band was used on a time reference basis to estimate the beamvectors of the rest of the bands. The underlying method was equivalent to the cross-SCORE algorithm [6]. The key feature of these methods was the existence of a fully correlated signal of interest and uncorrelated interferences in the two branches of interest.

In the present paper, the benefit of the estimation the beamvectors using all the N frequency bands or diversity branches jointly, instead of just two, is investigated. After introducing the signal model for FDSS in Section 2, two different methods to obtain optimum beamvectors in the sense of maximum SINR are derived and analytically analyzed in Sections 3 and 4. Simulation results in terms of bit error rate (BER) are given in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6, the conclusions are drawn.

2. SIGNAL MODEL FOR FDSS

The FDSS model considered herein utilizes a simple repetition code ($N, 1$) [1] and, optionally, a different spreading code for each of the N frequency bands (see Fig.1) so that, after despreading, the possibly correlated interfering signals appear completely uncorrelated from band to band.

Assuming a quasi-static flat fading (constant in a burst basis), which is a reasonable assumption because the available bandwidth has already been partitioned into N bands, the snapshot received

with an array of Q elements for the frequency bin k is defined, after a possible despreading stage, as

$$\mathbf{x}_k(t) = s_d(t)\mathbf{a}_{d,k} + \sum_{i=1}^{I_k} s_{i,k}(t)\mathbf{a}_{i,k} + \mathbf{n}_k(t) \quad (1)$$

where $s_d(t)$ ($s_{i,k}(t)$) is the desired (i th interfering) temporal signal in band k , $\mathbf{a}_{d,k}$ ($\mathbf{a}_{i,k}$) is the generalized steering vector (generated by the superposition of many rays) of the desired (i th interfering) signal in band k (including the effect of the flat fading), $\mathbf{n}_k(t)$ is the AWG noise vector of band k , and I_k is the number of interfering signals in band k . Note that the desired signal $s_d(t)$ is fully correlated among the N frequency bins, whereas neither the interfering signals nor the noise are.

Since each frequency band undergoes a different flat fading and, in general, each band has a different interfering scenario¹, it appears imperative the use of N different beamvectors. Each one specifically designed to spatially null out the interfering signals and to steer towards the desired one. The received signal in frequency band k is, after beamforming with the beamvector $\mathbf{w}_k$,

$$y_k(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{x}_k(t). \quad (2)$$

It is noteworthy that the beamforming methods described hereinafter are completely applicable to the fast Frequency Hopping (FH) communication technique due to the straightforward parallelism between both systems. In FDSS, the desired signal is simultaneously transmitted through N frequency bands. In fast FH, the hopping frequency is faster than the symbol rate and, therefore, it can be seen as the consecutive transmission of the same signal through N frequency bands.

Taking into account the effect of the spatial processing on the subsequent stages in the receiver, the sufficient statistic for optimum detection is given by [5]:

$$\Lambda_n = \sum_{k=1}^N y_k(nT_s) \left(\frac{w_{kd}^*}{\sum_{i=1}^{I_k} p_{i,k} |w_{ki}|^2 + N_0 \|\mathbf{w}_k\|^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where T_s is the sampling period, $w_{kj} = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{a}_{k,j}$ is the response of the combiner to signal j in band k , and N_0 is thermal noise power density.

3. DIRECT N-DIVERSITY SELF-REFERENCE BEAMFORMING

The beamvectors are obtained in a blind manner using the property of cross-correlation, also termed self-reference or exact-prediction property [4, 5, 6]. This property stems from the fact that the desired signal is the only correlated component among the N branches, whereas the rest of the interfering signals or thermal noise are completely uncorrelated:

$$\mathbf{R}_{kl} = E \{ \mathbf{x}_k(t) \mathbf{x}_l^H(t) \} = p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \mathbf{a}_{d,l}^H \quad \text{for } k \neq l \quad (4a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_x^{(k)} &= \mathbf{R}_{kk} = E \{ \mathbf{x}_k(t) \mathbf{x}_k^H(t) \} \\ &= p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \mathbf{a}_{d,k}^H + \sum_{i=1}^{I_k} p_{i,k} \mathbf{a}_{i,k} \mathbf{a}_{i,k}^H + \mathbf{R}_n^{(k)}, \end{aligned} \quad (4b)$$

where $p_d = E \{ |s_d(t)|^2 \}$ and $p_{i,k} = E \{ |s_{i,k}(t)|^2 \}$. In such a situation, the desired component can be predicted from one branch to

¹Even with the same scenario, the DOAs and fadings of the rays corresponding to each band would be different, leading to different generalized steering vectors. Furthermore, the spatial signatures depend on the carrier frequency.

the other, being the prediction error due to the undesired interfering signals and becoming the objective to minimize.

The proposed design criterion is the minimization of the summation of the array output powers of all frequency bands, subject to a constraint to avoid the trivial solution (i.e., all-zero beamvectors):

$$\begin{aligned} &\min \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{R}_{kk} \mathbf{w}_k \\ \text{subject to } &\sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1, l \neq k}^N \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{R}_{kl} \mathbf{w}_l = \phi. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Note that the constraint has been carefully selected so that only the desired signal can contribute to it. Therefore, the beamvectors will cancel out all signals but the desired one.

This can be equivalently expressed as the maximization of the following Rayleigh quotient:

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1, l \neq k}^N \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{R}_{kl} \mathbf{w}_l}{\sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{R}_{kk} \mathbf{w}_k}, \quad (6)$$

which can be expressed in a matrix form as

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{w}^H \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{12} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{1N} \\ \mathbf{R}_{21} & \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}_{1N} & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{w} \\ &\mathbf{w}^H \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{11} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{22} & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{NN} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{w} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = [\mathbf{w}_1^T \quad \mathbf{w}_2^T \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{w}_N^T]^T$ is the stacked beamvector. The previous quotient can be further compacted as:

$$\frac{\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{R}_x \mathbf{w}}{\mathbf{w}^H (\mathbf{R}_x \odot \text{kron}(\mathbf{I}_N, \mathbf{1}_Q)) \mathbf{w}} - 1 \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_x = E \{ \mathbf{x}(t) \mathbf{x}(t)^H \}$,

$\mathbf{x}(t) = [\mathbf{x}_1^T(t) \quad \mathbf{x}_2^T(t) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{x}_N^T(t)]^T$ is the stacked snapshot, $\odot$ represents the Hadamard product, $\text{kron}(\cdot, \cdot)$ the Kronecker product, $\mathbf{I}_N \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the identity matrix, and $\mathbf{1}_Q \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times Q}$ the all-one matrix. The solution to the maximization of the previous Rayleigh quotient is given by the generalized eigenvector corresponding to the maximum generalized eigenvalue:

$$\mathbf{R}_x \mathbf{w} = \lambda_{\max} (\mathbf{R}_x \odot \text{kron}(\mathbf{I}_N, \mathbf{1}_Q)) \mathbf{w}, \quad (9)$$

which gives directly the solution for all the beamvectors in a joint manner.

Note that for the case of just two bands ($N=2$), the quotient (6) reduces to:

$$\frac{\mathbf{w}_1^H E \{ \mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}_2^H \} \mathbf{w}_2 + \mathbf{w}_2^H E \{ \mathbf{x}_2 \mathbf{x}_1^H \} \mathbf{w}_1}{\mathbf{w}_1^H E \{ \mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}_1^H \} \mathbf{w}_1 + \mathbf{w}_2^H E \{ \mathbf{x}_2 \mathbf{x}_2^H \} \mathbf{w}_2} \quad (10)$$

which is identical to the method proposed in [5], in which only two branches were used for the self-reference beamvector estimation.

3.1. Analysis of the solution

The eigenvector equation that maximizes (7) can be expressed, incorporating (4a), as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{11}^{-1} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{NN}^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,1} \sum_{k=1, k \neq 1}^N w_{kd}^* \\ \vdots \\ p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,N} \sum_{k=1, k \neq N}^N w_{kd}^* \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_{\max} \mathbf{w} \quad (11)$$

where $w_{kd} = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{a}_{d,k}$ is the response of the combiner to the desired signal in band k . Therefore, it has been shown that the proposed blind method yields the optimum Wiener solution that can be shown to maximize the signal to interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) [11]:

$$w_k = \alpha_k \mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k}^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \quad (12)$$

where $\alpha_k = p_d \lambda_{\max}^{-1} \sum_{l \neq k}^N w_{ld}^*$ is simply a scalar value. It can also be proved that the scalars α_k are all nonzero values (see Appendix).

4. PARALLEL N-DIVERSITY SELF-REFERENCE BEAMFORMING

In this section, the optimum beamvector for each band will be obtained independently, aiming at a parallel implementation. For each band k , we will consider the real branch k and its corresponding virtual branch composed of the rest of the bands:

$$y_k(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{x}_k(t) \quad (13)$$

$$\tilde{y}_k(t) = \sum_{\substack{l=1 \\ l \neq k}}^N \mathbf{w}_l^H \mathbf{x}_l(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k^H \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k(t) \quad (14)$$

where

$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k(t) = [\mathbf{x}_1^T(t), \dots, \mathbf{x}_{k-1}^T(t), \mathbf{x}_{k+1}^T(t), \dots, \mathbf{x}_N^T(t)]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(N-1)Q \times 1}$ is a stacked snapshot lacking $\mathbf{x}_k(t)$, and similarly $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{(N-1)Q \times 1}$ is a stacked beamvector lacking $\mathbf{w}_k$.

The design of the beamvectors $\mathbf{w}_k$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k$ will be based again on the property of exact self-prediction [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min E \{ |y_k(t) - \tilde{y}_k(t)|^2 \} \\ \text{subject to } \text{Re} \{ E \{ y_k(t) \tilde{y}_k^*(t) \} \} = \phi \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

It is very important to note that the desired component does not appear in the error minimization and, at the same time, it is the only component that can contribute to the constraint. As a result, the beamvector will steer towards the desired signal while spatially nulling out the rest of the signals present in the scenario.

An alternative and equivalent design criterion can be derived from the self-reference or cross-correlation property by maximizing the following Rayleigh quotient [5]:

$$\max \frac{\text{Re} \{ E \{ y_k(t) \tilde{y}_k^*(t) \} \}}{E \{ |y_k(t)|^2 \} + E \{ |\tilde{y}_k(t)|^2 \}} \quad (16)$$

or, as in [6],

$$\max \frac{|E \{ y_k(t) \tilde{y}_k^*(t) \}|^2}{E \{ |y_k(t)|^2 \} E \{ |\tilde{y}_k(t)|^2 \}}. \quad (17)$$

All the previously equivalent design criteria yield the following coupled equations (identical to (9)):

$$\mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k = \lambda_{\max} \mathbf{R}_{x_k x_k} \mathbf{w}_k \quad (18a)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k x_k} \mathbf{w}_k = \lambda_{\max} \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k \tilde{x}_k} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k \quad (18b)$$

where the covariance matrices are defined as usual. Note that $\mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k} = p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{d,k}^H$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{d,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N-1)Q \times 1}$ is a stacked vector containing the steering vectors of the desired signals of all frequency bands but $\mathbf{a}_{d,k}$. From eqs.(18a) and (18b), the uncoupled equation for the desired beamvector can be easily derived:

$$\left(\mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k} \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k \tilde{x}_k}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k x_k} \right) \mathbf{w}_k = \lambda_{\max}^2 \mathbf{R}_{x_k x_k} \mathbf{w}_k \quad (19a)$$

which reduces to the method proposed in [5] for the case of $N=2$ frequency bands. Eq.(19a) gives independently the beamvector for band k ; therefore, it has to be computed, either in parallel or serial fashion, for all each band.

4.1. Analysis of the solution

Expressing in a matrix form (18a) and (18b), and taking into account the expressions for $\mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k x_k}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{x_k \tilde{x}_k} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k x_k} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{w} = \lambda_{\max} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{x_k x_k} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k \tilde{x}_k} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}, \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = [\mathbf{w}_k^T \quad \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k^T]^T$, it follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{x_k x_k}^{-1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{\tilde{x}_k \tilde{x}_k}^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p_d \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{d,k}^* \\ p_d \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{d,k} \mathbf{w}_{d,k}^* \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_{\max} \mathbf{w}, \quad (21)$$

where $w_{d,k} = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{a}_{d,k}$ and $\tilde{w}_{d,k} = \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k^H \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{d,k}$ are the responses of the combiners to the steering of the desired signal. We can then write

$$\mathbf{w}_k = \alpha_k \mathbf{R}_{x_k x_k}^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{d,k} \quad (22)$$

where α_k is a nonzero scalar (otherwise the constraint of (15) would not be satisfied). Therefore, the parallel self-reference method also yields the optimum Wiener solution that maximizes the SINR.

5. SIMULATIONS

In order to test the new proposed blind beamforming algorithms, Monte-Carlo simulations were performed with the following scenario. An FDSS communication system utilizing $N=5$ frequency bands with a relative bandwidth of 40% with respect to the center frequency ($f_c = 900\text{MHz}$), and transmitting bursts of 300 symbols was considered. The modulation formats utilized were BPSK and binary DPSK with $T_s = 1\mu\text{s}$. The signals were received with an array of $Q=7$ antenna elements and the weighting factors of the sufficient statistics for optimum detection were assumed to be known according to eq.(3). The received signals were distributed as follows. The desired signal had a DOA of 15° (E_b/N_0 varying from -15dB to 5dB) and was present and fully correlated in all the frequency bands. There were two BPSK interfering signals with DOAs of 0° and -30° (INR's of 30dB and 20dB) present in all the bands as well and, finally, another two BPSK interfering signals with DOA's of 50° and 80° (INR's of 40dB and 20dB) present only in half of the frequency bins. All the interfering signals were modelled as uncorrelated.

To model the angular spread of the steering vectors, a Laplacian Power Angular Spectrum with a power azimuth spread (AS) of 8 degrees—corresponding to an outdoor or outdoor-to-indoor scenario—was used according to [12]. The temporal dispersion of the channel was assumed to be negligible, which is a realistic assumption because the available bandwidth has already been divided into N bands, and for the same reason the symbol period cannot be too small. Therefore, a different flat fading was generated for each frequency band. A vehicular speed of 3 km/h was assumed.

In Fig.2, the performance of different methods is shown in terms of uncoded BER as a function of the received E_b/N_0 with an average $I_0/N_0 \simeq 31.6\text{dB}$. It can be seen how the two proposed methods (Direct N-joint and Paral-N-joint) significantly outperform both the self-reference method based on just two branches (2-DIV) and the classical time reference beamformer using 10% of the symbols as a training sequence (TRB). The difference of about 1dB to the optimum BER is due to the estimation of the covariance matrices. If a longer burst is used, i.e., 1000 symbols, the difference renders insignificant. Note that a receiver with a single antenna cannot work in such an adverse scenario.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Two new blind spatial processing algorithm for FDSS communication systems (also applicable to fast FH) have been proposed. They

Figure 2: Performance comparison in terms of BER of the different methods for beamforming in FDSS signalling schemes.

are derived based on the inherent frequency redundancy presented by the FDSS signalling scheme using the trivial repetition code. They utilize efficiently the joint N-fold cross-correlation properties presented by the N frequency bands.

Both presented methods have been analytically shown to yield optimum beamvectors in the sense of maximum SINR. They have also been tested via Monte-Carlo simulations, showing a performance close to the optimal one and clearly outperforming the already existing methods.

7. APPENDIX

To prove that the scalar values of (12) are nonzero, we rewrite the eigenvector equation, incorporating (12), as

$$p_d \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \rho_2 \mathbf{a}_{d,1} & \cdots & \rho_N \mathbf{a}_{d,1} \\ \rho_1 \mathbf{a}_{d,2} & \mathbf{0} & & \rho_N \mathbf{a}_{d,2} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_1 \mathbf{a}_{d,N} & \rho_2 \mathbf{a}_{d,N} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \alpha = \lambda_{\max} \mathbf{D}_{a_d} \alpha \quad (23)$$

where $\alpha = [\alpha_1^T \ \alpha_2^T \ \cdots \ \alpha_N^T]^T$,

$$\mathbf{D}_{a_d} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_{d,1} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{a}_{d,2} & & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{a}_{d,N} \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and}$$

$$\rho_k = \mathbf{a}_{d,k}^H \mathbf{R}_{kk}^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{d,k}.$$

Premultiplying this equation by matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_{d,1}^H \mathbf{R}_{11}^{-1} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{a}_{d,2}^H \mathbf{R}_{22}^{-1} & & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{a}_{d,N}^H \mathbf{R}_{NN}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

and then by $\mathbf{D}_\rho^{-1}$, where $\mathbf{D}_\rho = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \rho_2 & & 0 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \rho_N \end{bmatrix}$, it can

then be written as

$$p_d \left(\begin{bmatrix} \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \cdots & \rho_N \\ \rho_1 & \rho_2 & & \rho_N \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \cdots & \rho_N \end{bmatrix} - \mathbf{D}_\rho \right) \alpha = \lambda_{\max} \alpha \quad (24)$$

which can be finally expressed as

$$\left(\mathbf{1} \cdot \rho^T \right) \alpha = \left(\mathbf{D}_\rho + \frac{\lambda_{\max}}{p_d} \mathbf{I} \right) \alpha \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the all-one vector, and

$\rho = [\rho_1^T \ \rho_2^T \ \cdots \ \rho_N^T]^T$. From equation (25), and assuming $(\rho^T \alpha) \neq 0$, which necessarily holds so that the constraint of (5) is satisfied, it can be easily seen that equality

$$\left(\mathbf{D}_\rho + \frac{\lambda_{\max}}{p_d} \mathbf{I} \right) \alpha = \mathbf{1} (\rho^T \alpha) \quad (26)$$

cannot hold if any $\alpha_k = 0$.

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